

DEVELOPMENT OF THE PERSONALITY OF CHILDREN IN EARLY CHILDHOOD**Karimova Mukarramkhan Kholimovna**

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Abstract. The article describes the psychological, emotional, social and intellectual development of the child, a number of stages in which children learn to understand their feelings in early childhood, children learn to feel the world and themselves, and it is written that this process is the basis of their emotional development. They develop the senses of sight, hearing and touch, and it has been shown that they simultaneously acquire new knowledge and skills.

Keywords: psychological, emotional, social, intellectual, development, feeling, process, vision, hearing, feeling, sensations, knowledge, skill.

РАЗВИТИЕ ЛИЧНОСТИ ДЕТЕЙ В РАННЕМ ДЕТСТВЕ

Аннотация. В статье описывается психологическое, эмоциональное, социальное и интеллектуальное развитие ребенка, ряд этапов, на которых дети учатся понимать свои чувства в раннем детстве, дети учатся чувствовать мир и себя, и написано, что этот процесс является основой их эмоционального развития. У них развиваются чувства зрения, слуха и осязания, и показано, что они одновременно приобретают новые знания и навыки.

Ключевые слова: психологическое, эмоциональное, социальное, интеллектуальное, развитие, чувство, процесс, зрение, слух, чувство, ощущения, знание, навык.

INTRODUCTION

The development of children's personality in early childhood is a very important process.

During this period, the psychological, emotional, social and intellectual development of the child is mainly influenced by motherhood and parenthood. This period is often called the time that forms the main foundation of children's education and personality. Below are some key aspects of children's personality development. In early childhood, children begin to understand their feelings.

They receive mainly positive emotions from their parents, such as love, attention, safety and interest. This is important for creating a sense of security and stability in the child. After 1 year, children begin to express their emotions more. Their emotional relationships depend on the descriptions and interactions of their parents. In early childhood, the process of children understanding their feelings has its own characteristics.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Children go through a series of stages in learning to make sense of the world and themselves, a process that is fundamental to their emotional development.

Understanding emotions by age:

- Newborns: Newborns express their emotions only by asking for basic needs such as hunger, dryness, and comfort. Children this age tend to show only body control and automatic responses when expressing their feelings.

- Middle-aged children: After 6 months, children express their feelings more clearly. They recognize and demonstrate basic emotions such as joy, sadness, and fear (for example, by laughing or crying).

- Cognitive development and awareness of emotions: By 2-3 years, children notice differences between themselves and others, which develops emotional awareness. They begin to learn words to express their emotions, such as “I feel sad” and “I am happy.”

- Social interactions: By 4-5 years, children better understand their emotions as they establish social connections with others. They understand the feelings of others and begin to empathize with them. At this age, children learn to manage their emotions and adapt to social norms.

-Emotional self-awareness: As children develop, they understand their emotions in a more complex way. By the age of 6-7, children learn to understand their feelings not only internally, but also when communicating with others, imagining themselves in their place.

Intellectual development.

Children begin to learn about their environment in early childhood. They develop their senses, such as sight, hearing, and feeling, and at the same time acquire new knowledge and skills.

Between the ages of 1 and 3, children begin to speak, which gives them the opportunity to express themselves and communicate with others. During this period, there is active brain development. Children begin to learn about their environment in early childhood. This process is a very important stage of development, during which they receive and experience a lot of new information. They begin to perceive the world through sounds, colors, shapes, feelings, and movements. This learning process is carried out mainly through the senses (sight, hearing, touch, smell, taste). Children also learn and form relationships with the people around them.

Social development. In early childhood, a child learns from relationships with parents or other family members. Children begin to master social roles and try to understand the world around them. After 2 years, children find their first friends and begin to communicate with each other, which helps develop social skills. In early childhood, a child's relationship with parents or other family members is very important for the child's emotional and social development.

Physical Development:

In early childhood, a child's physical development occurs very quickly. They develop simple motor skills such as holding their head up, walking, and moving their arms.

By the age of 2 or 3, children begin to act more independently, such as trying to complete everyday tasks such as eating and dressing themselves. Early childhood is a very important and turbulent period in a child's physical development. This period usually includes the period from birth to 6 years of age. Below are some important aspects of a child's physical development during early childhood. Brain and Nervous System Development: After birth, a child's brain and nervous system develop very quickly. Their brain size doubles within a year of birth. During this period, a child's brain quickly registers new knowledge and experiences. Skeletal and Muscular System: A child's skeleton (bones) and muscular system are developing. Bones become stronger over time, and bone mass increases. At the same time, muscles become stronger and coordination improves.

Action Management: In early childhood, children quickly learn new motor (movement) skills. Newborns are usually able to hold their heads up for only a short time, but after a few months they gain full control of their arms and legs. At 6 months and later, children begin to pick up objects with their hands and explore them. Event and physical skills. During this period, children develop their physical abilities. From the age of 1, children try to stand up, walk and run. At the age of 2-3, they develop skills such as running, jumping, untying. Sensorimotor development.

Sensorimotor development strengthens the connection between the child's senses (eyes, ears, smell, taste and touch) and the motor system. This ensures that the child has a good understanding of the world around him and control over his actions. Balance and coordination: children learn to maintain balance and use all muscle groups in a balanced manner. By the age of 4-5, they begin to perform more complex physical activities, for example, performing playful exercises such as riding a bike, running faster or playing a little chess. 5. Personality and self-awareness. During this period, children try to understand their "I". They become aware of their identity, gender, and other unique characteristics. During this time, the child tries to satisfy their basic needs and forms an initial idea of their personality. "Meeting the child's basic needs" means understanding and providing for all the basic needs for the child's development. These needs differ from a psychological, physiological, and social point of view. Their main types are as follows.

Physiological needs. The child needs the necessary conditions for health, adequate nutrition, sleep, and physical activity. These basic needs affect the child's physical development.

Emotional and psychological needs. The child needs love, attention, and warmth. The child needs to feel the support of a parent or another adult in order to feel safe and accepted. Social needs. The child develops social skills through social communication, play, and contact with other people. This is especially necessary for communicating with friends and integrating into society.

Educational needs. The child is ready to learn and gain new knowledge. These needs are the basis for the child's mental development and future success. Meeting these needs of the child is necessary for his or her healthy development and happy life.

CONCLUSION

Early childhood is an important stage in human development. During this period, a child develops emotional, intellectual, physical and social skills and forms the foundation of his future personality. Parents and other caregivers play an important role in influencing the child's development. In early childhood, when children learn to understand their emotions, their relationships with their parents and the adults around them are very important. They help children name, express and manage their feelings, which develops children's emotional awareness. Thus, relationships with family members in childhood shape a child's life and have a great influence on his social and emotional development. Thus, early childhood lays an important foundation for the child's physical development, which will help him in the future to develop motor and sports activities.

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